

The Pattern of High Refractive Error in Pakistan

ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of the study was to find out the pattern of high refractive error

Study Design: Cross sectional study

Place and Duration of Study: Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi from Feb, 2018 to Aug, 2018.

Material and Methods: 203 HRE patient data was included in this study. The verbal consent was taken from the patient before taking the data. All the patients who visited the eye clinic were consulted by qualified optometrists and ophthalmologists. The purposive and convenient sampling technique was selected for data collection. The data was collected from the one to one patient interviews and patient medical record. SPSS and Microsoft excel was used for data analysis.

Results: A total number of 5871 patients visited BBH eye clinic from Feb, 2018 to Aug, 2018. The refractive error patients were 2748 (46.81%) among them. The high refractive error patients among the refractive error patients were 203. Among the HRE patients, 42.21% were myopia patients, 19.48% were hyperopia patients, and 38.31% were astigmatism patients. In astigmatic high refractive error patients, 49.15% were with the rule astigmatism patients, 31.36% were against the rule astigmatism patients and 19.49% were oblique astigmatism patients.

Conclusion: The current study indicates that the HRE frequency is very high from the expectation. The HRE may lead toward the blindness. The awareness and primary eye care can play a role to minimize this issue.

Keywords: High refractive error, Astigmatism, Myopia, Hyperopia

INTRODUCTION

World Health Organization estimated that globally 0.96% children are visually impaired due to uncorrected refractive error or inadequately corrected refractive error. It is estimated that 12.8 million children are visually impaired with age's ranges from 5 years to 15 years. The urban areas and semi urban areas are more affected than rural areas.^{1,2} World Health Organization calculated the uncorrected refractive error cost. There are two types of losses which are related with the uncorrected refractive error. These losses are direct and indirect losses. These losses can make a significant impact on the employee work, organizational performance and country GDP. The world productivity loss due to uncorrected refractive error is almost 202 billion US dollars. And five years addressing problem cost is almost 28 billion US dollars.^{2,3,4}

In many of the developed and developing countries the leading cause of preventable blindness is uncorrected refractive error.^{5,6} This condition is very alarming for the world. The more eye care professionals are needed to be trained for the eye care services provision at primary (community), secondary and tertiary level like ophthalmologists, optometrists and opticians. The uncorrected refractive errors can be corrected through the provision of spectacles and contact lenses. The refractive surgery is one of the more advanced and very expensive techniques to correct refractive error. Mostly the refractive surgery is good for elite class persons to correct their refractive error.^{7,8}

Presbyopia is an age related eye problem which is related with the loss of accommodation. This condition starts after 40-45 years of age. Most of the persons experience this condition in older ages. Worldwide surveys including the World Health Organization survey, UNESCO survey, World Bank survey and many other reputed organizations surveys exclude presbyopia from the refractive error surveys. But World Health Organization recognized its effect on the GDP of country, employee productivity, organizational productivity and quality of life. World Health Organization highlighted the unmet need of presbyopia correction.^{9,10} The frailty is associated with the refractive error among the elders.¹¹ According to the World Health Organization estimate almost 153 million people are with uncorrected refractive error throughout the world. The estimated productivity loss due to uncorrected refractive error is ranges between 121- 427 billion US dollars.¹²

The high and low income countries are economically affected with the refractive error.¹³ The rate of refractive error correction is higher in urban area as compared to rural and suburban areas. The refractive error correction rate is low in south Asia like Pakistan, Bangladesh, and India etc.¹⁴ In 20th century, the refractive error cases was increasing and the most common increasing refractive error was myopia.^{15,16} There are many causes of visual impairment but the most common causes of visual impairment are uncorrected refractive error and blindness.¹⁷ The uncorrected refractive error population is lower in developed countries and higher in the developing and undeveloped countries.¹⁸

The significance of this study is to provide valuable research based information to the ministry of health, eye health policy making organizations, planning division, and non-profitable organizations for their future directions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This was a cross sectional study design to collect the data of 203 patients attended the eye OPD of Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi with refractive error from Feb, 2018 to Aug, 2018. The verbal consent was taken from the patient before taking the data. All the patients who visited the eye clinic were consulted by qualified optometrists and ophthalmologists. Patients with refractive error were referred to refraction clinic from the general eye OPD for refractive error management. The purposive and convenient sampling technique was selected for data collection. The detailed data was collected from patients with high refractive error. The data was collected from the willing patients and the data of non-willing patients was skipped. The data was collected from the one to one patient interviews and patient medical record. The patient demographic data and other clinical data were recorded on specially designed questionnaire. This questionnaire was designed with group discussion among the eye care researchers and qualified clinical optometrists. The criteria selected for spherical refractive error was $\pm 6.00D$ for cylindrical refractive error was $\pm 2.50 DC$. The patients with high refractive error and willing to participate were included in this study. All the patients included in this study underwent through the ocular examination and their high refractive error managed through the pair of glasses, contact lenses and refractive surgery. The patients with mental problems and non-willing patients were excluded from the study. The collected data was managed and analyzed through SPSS.

RESULTS

A total number of 5871 patients visited BBH eye clinic from Feb, 2018 to Aug, 2018. The refractive error patients were 2748 (46.81%) among them. The high refractive error patients among the refractive error patients were 203. The frequency of HRE among the total eye OPD was 3.46%. The mean age of high refractive error subjects was 30.4 years. Among the high refractive error patients the 47.80% were males and 52.20% were females. The 48.30% subjects were with monocular HRE and 51.70% subjects were with binocular HRE. The ages of patients were categorized into different groups. 28.6% patient's age group was 0-15 years, 33% patient's age group was 16-30 years, 16.7% patient's age group was 31-45 years, 13.8% patient's age group was 46-60 and 7.9% patient's age group was 60+ years. 22.20% high refractive error patients visited first time eye clinic and 77.80% HRE patients already visited eye clinics and already have refractive error management material like glasses and contact lenses etc.

Table 1: Frequency of myopia, hyperopia and astigmatism in HRE patients

HRE	Myopia	Hyperopia	Astigmatism
203	42.21%	19.48%	38.31%
Astigmatism	With the rule	Against the rule	Oblique
	49.15%	31.36%	19.49%

N=203, HRE = high refractive error

Among the HRE patients, 42.21% were myopia patients, 19.48% were hyperopia patients, and 38.31% were astigmatism patients. In astigmatic high refractive error patients, 49.15% were with the rule astigmatism patients, 31.36% were against the rule astigmatism patients and 19.49% were oblique astigmatism patients. Among the high refractive error patients, 38.14 % were compound myopic astigmatism patients, 36.44% were mixed astigmatism patients, 11.86% were simple myopic astigmatism patients, 9.32% were simple hyperopic astigmatism patients and 4.24% were compound hyperopic astigmatism patients.

In high refractive error subjects, 59.72% patient's best corrected VA was 6/6, 13.43% patient's best corrected VA was 6/6p, 9.54% patient's best corrected VA was 6/9, 7.42% patient's best

corrected VA was 6/12, 3.16% patient's best corrected VA was 6/18 and 6.71% patient's best corrected VA was worse than 6/18. The refractive error patients were managed through the glasses, contact lenses and refractive surgery.

Table 2: Frequency of HRE management

HRE Management	Spectacles	Contact Lenses	R. Surgery
203	90.10%	8.40%	1.50%

N=203, R. Surgery = refractive surgery

90.10% HRE patients were managed through spectacles, 8.40% subjects were advised to use contact lenses to manage their HRE and 1.50% patients were advised to manage their HRE through refractive surgery. 85.20% HRE patients were advised to use conventional spectacle lenses, 8.20% patients were advised to use high index spectacle lenses and 6.20% patients were advised to use aspheric spectacle lenses.

DISCUSSION

In this cross sectional study it was the frequency of high refractive error was high. This situation may lead toward the permanent vision loss like pathological myopia. The frequency of refractive error founded in this study was 46.81%. The frequency of high refractive error founded in this is very high as compared to the frequency of refractive error was 10.80% of eye OPD of tertiary eye care hospital of Nepal.¹⁹ There is a huge difference of RE frequencies in Pakistan and Nepal. The reason behind it is the cultural differences, the demographics differences, social life differences, the quality of life differences, medical knowledge differences and economy differences of both countries. The refractive error frequency of one of the study which was conducted in Pakistan was 48.16%.²⁰ The results of this study are closer to our study (46.81%). The study results of these two studies are almost similar.

The different ethnicity population has myopia and the ethnicity of population does not affect the presence of myopia. So we can say now myopia is a universal condition.^{16,21} This worldwide presence of myopia is now a one of the major public health concern. The rapid urbanization is

one of the causes behind it.²² The refractive error burden of 15-49 years old young population is very high.²³ The spectacle coverage of our refractive error was very low in some of the countries like India and Eritrea.^{24,25}

This study results declared that myopic refractive error is most common high refractive error, astigmatism is second most common and hyperopia is the least common high refractive error. As for the astigmatism, the myopic astigmatism was more common as compared to hyperopic astigmatism and mixed astigmatism.

The limitations of the study were limited resources, cross sectional study design, questionnaire with limited number of questions and the quality of life and social interaction questions which can provide more information about the personal problems of HRE patient was missing. The future researchers should work on the social interactions, quality of life, and family history and HRE linkage with other ocular problems. The longitudinal study design should be adopted in future for depth information about the HRE.

CONCLUSION

The frequency of HRE is very high from the expectation level. The very high refractive error may lead toward the blindness. The awareness about the eye health and refractive error can reduce this HRE issue. The primary eye care services and school screening programs can be very helpful to minimize the HRE.

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